

Controversial Issues in Biology: Are neurons the only cells in the brain driving behavior?

Abigail Armlin and Rosayla Gonzalez

Department of Biological Sciences, University of New Hampshire

General Introduction

Current and Controversial Issues in Biology (BIOL 700) is a seminar-style class at the University of New Hampshire. The structure of the class is as follows: The class follows a repeating template of selecting a controversial issue proposed by UNH faculty members, finding 20 research papers on said topic, and encouraging the classroom to engage with and discuss the various papers selected for each topic. 3-4 days were allotted to reviewing and discussing each topic, with each topic of discussion being led by a group of 2-3 students in the class. 10 pro and 10 con papers were selected per topic, reviewed, and discussed. For each paper, three questions were asked about specific details of the article. One paper from each topic was chosen by each student to thoroughly review the paper and prepare a summary for the class to discuss, and answer the three questions. This allowed for more intensive understanding of the papers collectively, giving better insight into the topics at hand than if we had just read the abstract/Google search results. The class had an open discussion of each topic/paper, allowing thoughts on each paper to be shared. After reviewing all sources, the class was polled to form a stance on whether we collectively agreed we should enact the topic actions. The vote was on a scale of 1 to 10, with 1 indicating strong opposition to the controversial issue and 10 representing full support. The votes were averaged to determine the class's overall position on the topic.

Brain cells governing behavior

This topic debunks the previous notion that neurons were the only cells in the brain driving behavior (Theodosius et al., 2007, Fishell & Heintz, 2013). The research question was: are neurons the sole drivers of behavior, or do other brain cells (e.g., glia, vascular, immune) also play direct roles? To lay some foundation, there are two categories of cells in the brain (Szczepanski & Knight, 2014). Neurons are the main information-processing units of the brain, which transmit signals throughout the body. The structure of the neuron consists of a cell body called a soma, dendrites to receive signals, and axons which send signals to other cells. There are various kinds of neurons depending on their function within the specific region of the brain. The

second category of brain cells is called glial cells. These cells surround and support neurons; there are multiple types that play different roles in supporting neural activity (Filley, 2005). Some of their functions consist of: providing nutrients, speeding up signal transmission, and acting as brain immune cells.

In the past 20-30 years, with technological advancements, discoveries about the brain are being made (Kang et al., 2020a). Before this time period, the concept of what determines behavior was concrete in that neurons do all of the “computing,” and glia cells are supporters. However, recent discoveries have pointed towards non-neural cells playing a larger role in cognition and behavior. For instance, some research suggests that our gut microbiome and immune system play a role in human behavior (Dinan et al., 2015; Bilbo & Schwarz, 2012; McEwen, 2020; Sylvia & Demas, 2018)

What are the pros?

Having multiple types of cells in the brain driving behavior, not just neurons, is a major advantage as it allows for more complex, efficient, and flexible control of brain function. Although neurons play a major role in transmitting electrical signals that initiate behaviors, other brain cells, such as glial cells, support and regulate these activities (Kelly & Terrana, 2004; Kang et al., 2020; Adamsky et al., 2018; Parkhurst et al., 2013; Nagai et al., 2021). Astrocytes help maintain the chemical environment around neurons and influence synaptic activity (Adamsky et al., 2018; Nagai et al., 2021), while microglia, the brain’s immune cells, monitor for damage (Parkhurst et al., 2013). Together, these cells come together to form a coordinated network in the brain and with this cellular diversity, it makes the brain more adaptable, stable, and capable of supporting the complex behaviors seen in humans.

What are the cons?

Having only neurons driving behavior, without the involvement of other brain cells, would be a major disadvantage because it would limit the brain’s complexity and adaptability. For a long time, scientists assumed that neurons alone controlled behavior, which made it difficult to fully understand how the brain worked (Buzsáki & Vöröslakos, 2023; Karnath et al., 2018). It wasn’t until more advanced research and imaging techniques emerged that scientists discovered how important non-neuronal cells are for brain signaling, repair, and learning. Traditional neuroscience

research has historically focused almost entirely on neurons, often overlooking non-neuronal cells (Dalglish et al., 2020; (Krashes et al., 2013; (Lee et al., 2016; Donahue & Kreitzer, 2015; Dietrich et al., 2015). This realization transformed neuroscience, showing that behavior arises from the interaction of many cell types (Kang et al., 2020; Parkhurst et al., 2013; Delcourte et al., 2023), not just neurons and highlights how important it is to study brain function as a whole instead of just trying to pin-point how neurons work, because when scientists limit themselves to only studying neurons they often miss out on very important components which include neuronal support and defense.

Pros and Cons Table

Neurons and glial cells work together to drive behavior (Pro)	Sources	Neurons are the only cell in the brain driving behavior (Con)	Sources
The importance of Astrocytes in behavior and decision-making	<i>Kang et al., 2020</i> <i>Theodosis et al., 2007</i>	Neurons alone can trigger sensory perception	<i>Dalglish et al., 2020</i>
The importance of microglia cells in learning and neural plasticity	<i>Parkhurst et al., 2013</i>	Neuronal circuits regulate feeding and motivation	<i>Krashes et al., 2013</i> <i>Dietrich et al., 2015</i>
The importance of Astrocytes in memory and cognition	<i>Adamsky et al., 2018,</i> <i>Nagai et al., 2021</i>	Movement is driven by neuronal circuits	<i>Lee et al., 2016</i> <i>Donahue & Kreitzer, 2015</i>

<p>The influence of gut microbiota on human behavior and the brain</p>	<p><i>Dinan et al., 2015</i> <i>Sylvia & Demas, 2018</i></p>		
---	--	--	--

What do we think?

As students we believe it's important to include all brain cells when studying brain and behavior. While neurons are essential for transmitting signals and generating electrical activity, research now shows that other cell types, like astrocytes and microglia also play active roles in learning, memory, and decision-making. Ignoring these contributions gives us an incomplete picture of how the brain truly functions.

Understanding behaviors requires looking at how neurons and glial cells interact as a network, rather than focusing on one cell type alone. Recognizing the roles of all brain cells not only strengthens our understanding of neural processes but also opens the door to new approaches for studying and treating neurological and psychiatric disorders.

References

Adamsky, A., Kol, A., Kreisel, T., Doron, A., Ozeri-Engelhard, N., Melcer, T., Refaeli, R., Horn, H., Regev, L., Groysman, M., London, M., & Goshen, I. (2018). Astrocytic Activation Generates *De Novo* Neuronal Potentiation and Memory Enhancement. *Cell*, *174*(1), 59-71.e14.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2018.05.002>

Bilbo, S. D., & Schwarz, J. M. (2012). The immune system and developmental programming of brain and behavior. *Frontiers in Neuroendocrinology*, *33*(3), 267–286.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yfrne.2012.08.006>

Buzsáki, G., & Vöröslakos, M. (2023). Brain rhythms have come of age. *Neuron*, *111*(7), 922–926. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2023.03.018>

Dalgleish, H. W., Russell, L. E., Packer, A. M., Roth, A., Gauld, O. M., Greenstreet, F., Thompson, E. J., & Häusser, M. (2020). How many neurons are sufficient for perception of cortical activity? *eLife*, *9*, e58889. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.58889>

Delcourte, S., Bouloufa, A., Rovera, R., Bétry, C., Abrial, E., Dkhissi-Benyahya, O., Heinrich, C., Marcy, G., Raineteau, O., Haddjeri, N., Lucas, G., & Etiévant, A. (2023). Chemogenetic activation of prefrontal astroglia enhances recognition memory performance in rat. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, *166*, 115384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2023.115384>

Dietrich, M. O., Zimmer, M. R., Bober, J., & Horvath, T. L. (2015). Hypothalamic Agrp Neurons Drive Stereotypic Behaviors beyond Feeding. *Cell*, *160*(6), 1222–1232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2015.02.024>

Dinan, T. G., Stilling, R. M., Stanton, C., & Cryan, J. F. (2015). Collective unconscious: How gut microbes shape human behavior. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, *63*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2015.02.021>

Donahue, C. H., & Kreitzer, A. C. (2015). A Direct Path to Action Initiation. *Neuron*, *88*(2), 240–241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2015.10.013>

Filley, C. M. (2005). White Matter and Behavioral Neurology. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, *1064*(1), 162–183. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1340.028>

Fishell, G., & Heintz, N. (2013). The Neuron Identity Problem: Form Meets Function. *Neuron*, *80*(3), 602–612. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2013.10.035>

Kang, S., Hong, S.-I., Lee, J., Peyton, L., Baker, M., Choi, S., Kim, H., Chang, S.-Y., & Choi, D.-S. (2020a). Activation of Astrocytes in the Dorsomedial Striatum Facilitates Transition From Habitual to Goal-Directed Reward-Seeking Behavior. *Biological Psychiatry*, *88*(10), 797–808. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2020.04.023>

Kang, S., Hong, S.-I., Lee, J., Peyton, L., Baker, M., Choi, S., Kim, H., Chang, S.-Y., & Choi, D.-S. (2020b). Activation of Astrocytes in the Dorsomedial Striatum Facilitates Transition From Habitual to Goal-Directed Reward-Seeking Behavior. *Biological Psychiatry*, *88*(10), 797–808. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2020.04.023>

Karnath, H.-O., Sperber, C., & Rorden, C. (2018). Mapping human brain lesions and their functional consequences. *NeuroImage*, *165*, 180–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.10.028>

Kelly, M. G., & Terrana, S. (2004). A Method to Teach Age-Specific Demography with Field Grown Rapid Cycling *Brassica rapa* (Wisconsin Fast Plants). *Journal of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Education*, *33*(1), 40–46. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jnrlse.2004.0040>

Krashes, M. J., Shah, B. P., Koda, S., & Lowell, B. B. (2013). Rapid versus Delayed Stimulation of Feeding by the Endogenously Released AgRP Neuron Mediators GABA, NPY, and AgRP. *Cell Metabolism*, *18*(4), 588–595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2013.09.009>

Lee, H. J., Weitz, A. J., Bernal-Casas, D., Duffy, B. A., Choy, M., Kravitz, A. V., Kreitzer, A. C., & Lee, J. H. (2016). Activation of Direct and Indirect Pathway Medium Spiny Neurons Drives Distinct Brain-wide Responses. *Neuron*, *91*(2), 412–424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2016.06.010>

McEwen, B. S. (2020). Hormones and behavior and the integration of brain-body science. *Hormones and Behavior*, *119*, 104619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2019.104619>

Nagai, J., Bellafard, A., Qu, Z., Yu, X., Ollivier, M., Gangwani, M. R., Diaz-Castro, B., Coppola, G., Schumacher, S. M., Golshani, P., Gradinaru, V., & Khakh, B. S. (2021). Specific and behaviorally consequential astrocyte Gq GPCR signaling attenuation in vivo with iβARK. *Neuron*, *109*(14), 2256–2274.e9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2021.05.023>

Parkhurst, C. N., Yang, G., Ninan, I., Savas, J. N., Yates, J. R., Lafaille, J. J., Hempstead, B. L., Littman, D. R., & Gan, W.-B. (2013). Microglia Promote Learning-Dependent Synapse Formation through Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor. *Cell*, *155*(7), 1596–1609.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2013.11.030>

Sylvia, K. E., & Demas, G. E. (2018). A gut feeling: Microbiome-brain-immune interactions modulate social and affective behaviors. *Hormones and Behavior*, *99*, 41–49.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2018.02.001>

Szczepanski, S. M., & Knight, R. T. (2014). Insights into Human Behavior from Lesions to the Prefrontal Cortex. *Neuron*, *83*(5), 1002–1018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2014.08.011>
Theodosis, D., Poulain, D., & Oliet, S. (2007). Activity-Dependent Structural and Functional Plasticity of Astrocyte-Neuron Interactions. *Physiological Reviews*, *88*(3).
<https://journals.physiology.org/doi/full/10.1152/physrev.00036.2007>